

A novel ionophoretic technique for the study of binary and ternary metal complexes

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Ionophoretic technique has been used for the study of Fe^{III}/Zn^{II}-adipate binary and Fe^{III}/Zn^{II}-adipate-NTA (nitrilo tri acetic acid) ternary complexes. The stability constants of metal adipate binary complexes are found to be 10^{3.62} and 10^{2.04} and the stability constants of metal adipate-NTA ternary complexes have been found to be 10^{6.67} and 10^{5.95} for Fe^{III} and Zn^{II} complexes respectively at $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄) and 25°.

Migration of ions of pure electrolyte solutions has been widely studied but migration in mixed electrolyte solutions has not as yet been much investigated. This paper deals with latter aspect.

In the present communication, an effort has been made to assess the stability constants of mononuclear binary and ternary complexes formed in a system containing various electrolyte ingredients. The simple electrophoretic tube used in earlier investigation¹ is used for these studies.

Results and discussion

Metal-adipic acid binary system :

Fig. 1 illustrates the relationship between absorbance differences and the pH's and thus gives an idea of the change of overall mobility of the metal ion species with change in hydrogen ion status of the systems containing Fe^{III} and Zn^{II} adipic acid. The first plateau in each case corresponds to a region of pH where metal ions were uncomplexed. Further increase of pH from this region onward which naturally leads to increase in ligating adipic acid anion concentration [HL⁻] and brings about a progressive decrease in overall ionic mobility of the metal ion species. This decrease indicates formation of complex of the metal ions with the ligand. A point is reached beyond which mobility of the metal ion species remains constant regardless of the increase

of pH of reaction mixture. This is the second plateau which corresponds to a pH region in which 1 : 1 complex is predominantly formed. Beyond this plateau increase of pH has no effect and mobility remains constant.

The overall mobility U is a composite parameter contributed by different ionic species of the metal ion and is given by the following equation,

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1K_1[L] + u_2K_1K_2[L]^2 + \dots}{1 + K_1[L] + K_1K_2[L]^2 + \dots}$$

where K 's are the stability constants of complexes and $[L]$ is the concentration of adipic acid anion. u 's are the ionic mobilities of different species of the metal ions which can be assessed from the plateau's of the figure. In the region between first and second plateau the system contains overwhelmingly a mixture of free metal ion and 1 : 1 complex. The existence of 1 : 2 complex can be excluded and hence the third term in the numerator and the denominator of the above equation can be justifiably neglected. U would be equal to $u_0 + u_1/2$ provided $K_1[L] = 1$. Accordingly the pH corresponding to the average value of u_0 and u_1 is found from the figure and with the knowledge of the dissociation constants of adipic acid ($pK_1 = 4.26$ and $pK_2 = 5.03$) the concentration of adipic acid ion at this pH is calculated. Its reciprocal gives the stability constants K_1 of the 1 : 1 complex. The value of the stability constants are reported in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Mobility curve, metal-adipic acid systems : (●) Fe^{III}, (x) Zn^{II}.

Table 1. Stability constants of metal-adipic and M-adipic acid-NTA complexes

$\mu = 0.1, \text{ temp.} = 25^\circ\text{C}$

Metal ion	Calculated values		Literature values		Ref. No.
	M-L	M-L-NTA	ML	M-L-NTA	
Fe ^{III}	3.62	6.67	-	-	-
Zn ^{II}	2.04	5.95	2.80	5.75	6, 7

Metal-adipic acid-NTA ternary system :

Fig. 2 depicts the observations of studies carried out in metal-adipic acid-NTA ternary complexes. These graphs clearly show the formation of two plateaus in each case. The first plateau corresponds to binary M-adipic acid complex whereas the second plateau corresponds to the formation of new complex.

Fig. 2. Mobility curve, metal-adipic acid-NTA systems : (●) Fe^{III}, (×) Zn^{II}.

This new complex may be mixed complexes of the type M-L-NTA or pure M-NTA complex. But with the help of related graphs of M-NTA complexes, it was found that the absorbance difference in case of new complex is not identical to M-NTA pure complex. Further this ternary complex has greater mobility than that of binary M-adipic acid complex hence these observations confirms the formation of mixed M-L-NTA complex.

For M-L-NTA complexes the stability constant K is calculated by using modified equation,

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K'[\text{NTA}^-]}{1 + K'[\text{NTA}^-]}$$

here u_0 and u_1 are the mobilities of ML and M-L-NTA complexes.

From the figures concentrations of NTA at which overall mobility is mean of the mobilities of the two plateaus is determined. The concentration of NTA anion at pH 7.0 for this NTA concentration is calculated. K' is obviously equal to $1/[\text{NTA}]$. All these values are also reported in Table 1 and clearly indicates the superior coordinating power of NTA anions to other dicarboxylic acid species.

The stability constant value of Fe^{III} and Zn^{II} are in the order Fe^{III} > Zn^{II}, which follows the Irving William's⁵ order for the stability constants of transition metal of first transition series. The difference in the experimental and literature values may be due to different experimental conditions.

Experimental*Metal-adipic acid binary system :*

One set of 15 ml solution containing $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ Zn^{II}, $0.1 M$ HClO₄ and $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ adipic acid was prepared at different pH values (by adding NaOH solution). In case of Fe^{III}, $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ Fe^{III}, $0.1 M$ HClO₄ and $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ adipic acid was used. 10 ml of this solution is taken in an electrophoretic tube and thermostated at 25°. The position of tube was adjusted in such a way that the level of the solution in one wide end arm reached a circular mark on it. This adjustment fixed the volume of the solution on both sides of the middle stopper. Two (0.5 × 0.5 cm) platinum electrodes were dipped in each arm cup and a 50 V potential difference was applied between them. Electrolysis of the solution was allowed for 45 minutes, after which the middle stopper of the tube is closed. The solution of the anodic compartment was taken out in a 15 ml flask. The Fe^{III} content of the anodic compartment was converted to thiocyanate² complex and absorbance was measured at 480 nm against a reagent blank and the zinc content of the solution was converted into a coloured complex with zincon and the absorbance at 620 nm was measured. These observation were taken at different pH's and are graphically represented in Fig. 1.

Metal-NTA binary system :

The experiments for binary complexes of Fe^{III}/Zn^{II}-NTA are prerequisite for the study of metal adipic acid-NTA ternary complexes. These studies have been carried out by Singh³ and Sameena⁴. The observations and results of their studies have been considered for comparison of observations found for ternary complexes.

Metal-adipic acid-NTA ternary system :

The study of ternary complexes was carried out by progressive addition of secondary ligand NTA from $1 \times 10^{-6} M$ to $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ at a fixed pH 7.0 to a mixture of metal ions and $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ adipic acid and $0.1 M$ perchloric acid. The reason behind keeping the reaction mixture at pH 7.0 is that much ahead of this pH the simple binary complexes of metal-adipic acid and M-NTA are formed and remain intact even beyond this pH. The amount of secondary ligand NTA was increased each time in the electrophoretic tube and the electrolysis of the solution and its observation were recorded each time as it was done in case of binary complexes. These observation are graphically represented in Fig. 2.

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